

Code-Switching on Interlocutors' Online English-Speaking Proficiency

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ABSTRACT

This study was undertaken primarily to determine the extent of the participants' code-switching and reasons for code-switching. This study utilized both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The gathering of data focused on the administration of the focus group discussion (FGD). A total of twenty-eight (28) third-year education students of San Isidro College, Malaybalay, Bukidnon was purposively chosen as participants of the study. Mean, Percentage, Standard Deviation, Frequency, and T-test were used to generate the findings of the study. The participants' English Proficiency level was determined using the Rubric on Student Oral Language Matrix (SOLOM) adapted from the Riverside County Seal of Multiliteracy (2008). Findings revealed that there was no association of English Oral speaking proficiency to the extent of code-switching among the participants. Results showed that the majority or more than half of the participants are code-switching inter-sententially at varying extents having low extent as the highest. Another result revealed that almost all of the participants code-switched intra-sententially with moderate extent as the highest. Generally, findings showed that the English-speaking proficiency level of the students in the five components is on the average or mid-level. Thus, the participants' linguistic skills and English language proficiency need to be enhanced.

Subject Area

English Proficiency

Keywords: *Code-Switching, Focus Group Discussion, Oral English-Speaking Proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

With the goal of attaining global competitiveness, English teachers in the Philippine Educational System have been mandated to teach using the English language as the medium of instruction. By doing so, students are projected to graduate with excellent ability in English language communication. Likewise, in the K- 12 program of the Philippines, one of the

competencies required to be achieved by Filipino students is effective oral communication skills. Knowing the fact that communicative competence is truly a necessity for the 21st-century learners, students should be equipped with essential skills for effective communication.

However, online Filipino students of today do not put ample effort into learning and understanding the English language though exposed every day to English via the internet. Moreover, due to the huge linguistic differences between the English language and the Philippine national language which is Filipino as well as other native languages which are the students' mother tongues, not all Filipino learners are proficient in learning English. Through an English-only-policy means of instruction, most students achieve success and become proficient in the English language. Filipinos, being multilingual consider English as a Second Language. However, uniting the universal language with the native language becomes a usual and habitual practice among Filipinos. Combining the English language with other languages like Tagalog or Cebuano in utterances is called code-switching.

Code-switching is mainly used by people who uttered varieties of languages or more than one language. It is recognized that speakers who shift words from one direction to another in their oral communication are identified as code switchers. This phenomenon occurs when native and non-native speakers temporarily utter words with different kinds of languages. Code-switching predominantly arises mostly in multilingual societies. As Aranoff and Miller (2003) stated, many linguists have strained that bilingual communities have the power to choose their independence in communicating with other people as a means of styles and modes.

Code-switching, according to Kasperczyk (2015) is the alternation between two codes (both languages and dialects), among people who share those two particular enigmas. This pointed out that the use of more than one language alternates in one conversation or speech (Karjo, 2015). It is an everyday reality in every place where more than one language is spoken in everyday conversation. In an online classroom, there's a widespread perception that Filipino teachers and students freely code-switch. Students' interactions and their expressions disclosed that code-switching is a structure that learners resort to, intentionally or intuitively, to achieve the communicative goals mentioned by Amorim (2012).

There are several possible reasons why students engage in code-switching practices. One of the most frequent explanations of why bilinguals engage in code-switching practices is that they do it to compensate for a lack of language adeptness. Nyambura (2015) noted code-switching comes with different reasons why people tend to do code-switching namely: lack of language proficiency, to emphasize or stress on a particular point, lack of confidence, to explain a word, and to express personal emotions freely.

Moreover, code-switching can be used for self-expression and it is a way of shifting language for the sake of personal purposes. It is also used to build a sort of intimacy among members of a bilingual society. The art of code-switching encourages students for code-switching practices as a manner of expressing their thoughts, feelings, and emotions without inhibitions. Expressing ones' emotions, feelings, thoughts, and ideas in the English language requires eloquence in such language. But some students lack the confidence, skills, and articulateness in speaking the language thus resort to code-switching.

Another possible reason is, code-switching can be acknowledged as language preference. Students may apprehend code-switching as a tolerable practice in conversation not only in school but also in another communication scenario. Students may feel comfortable in language switching in their everyday communication. Abad (2005) noted that code-switching managed to lower the affective filter, and this consequently established rapport and created an atmosphere of informality, thus, allowing any learner to actively participate in the classroom discussion. Inhibitions would be narrowed and learning comes in.

Probyn (2010) observed that the most prominent method that teachers used was code-switching to attain a number of communicative ends. Furthermore, code-switching helps to facilitate the implication of classroom instruction since the teachers do not have to spend so much time trying to explain to the learners or searching for the simplest words to help to clear the students' understanding. However, many researchers believe that code-switching causes confusion, misperception and deteriorates the proficiency of students in English speaking. It delays the learners in acquiring high cognitive abilities because they are taught in two languages simultaneously in an unsystematic process.

Many school administrators view this code-switching practice as undesirable and adverse because they believe it is detrimental or damaging to the English language development among the students. Martin (2006) mentioned that the language preferences of teachers and students are often recognized as the reasons behind the continuing deterioration of English language proficiency among Filipino students.

Generally, code-switching among students is a habitual practice which is a problem in Philippine classrooms. It hinders and impedes the students' fluency development in verbal communication. At present, code-switching has become an undesirable practice in many parts of the world. In multilingual countries like the Philippines and Malaysia code-switching has emerged as a new language diversity (Bautista, 2004). Thus, this study sought to determine the influence of code-switching on interlocutors' English Oral proficiency at San Isidro College, Malaybalay, Bukidnon.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study sought to determine the classification of the code-switching practices, the level of the students' oral English proficiency, and the reasons for code-switching among students. Specifically, this study aimed answer the succeeding questions:

1. What is the participants' extent of code-switching in terms of the following classifications?
 - 1.1 inter-sentential;
 - 1.2 intra-sentential; and
 - 1.3 intra-word?
2. What is the participants' level of Oral Proficiency?
3. Is the participants' extent of code-switching significantly associated with their Oral English Proficiency?
4. Why do the participants code-switch?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on Odlin's Arm-Chair Model. The model posits that the switching behaviors that take place for comprehensible communication is a process that occurs in second language acquisition. Odlin's Arm-Chair Model is used to provide an explanation of how the language process works while either acquiring or learning a second language. The theory or model features two major terms, control and automaticity. These two processes occur after two language systems (L1 and L2) are mastered. It means that the use of two languages is dependent on the level of comprehension that has been accomplished throughout the process.

Once the speaker has achieved proficiency in two or more languages, automaticity will take place. This is a product of the control that the speaker has over those linguistic structures. Code-switching is an automatic process, which allows speakers switch from one language to another. The emphasis of the study is on the extent of Code-switching which is classified as Inter-sentential, Intra-Sentential, and Intra-Word. Over decades, various studies have shown that switching occurs inter-sententially, that is between sentences or clauses, as well as intra-sententially, within sentences or clauses.

In inter-sentential code-switching, the switching of language occurs in the sentence boundaries. This is perceived most often among the eloquent multilingual speakers. In intra-sentential code-switching, the switching of language occurs in between the sentences with no disruptions, reluctance, or pauses indicating a shifting of language. The speaker unintentionally does the shifting of language. Different forms of language switching occur within the clause and words. While in Intra-Word, there is an insertion of a word from one language to another (Esen, 2016).

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-method both qualitative and quantitative which helped analyze the most common practices of code-switching. The qualitative method provided the main perspective for the research. Through this method, the information gathered from the transcribed interviews was used to reinforce the code-switching practices. Through the quantitative method, students' responses were tabulated for frequencies and percentages. These were gathered in determining the specific descriptors of the reasons why students engage in code-switching. Through qualitative analysis, data were interpreted using mean rating to describe the level and extent of code-switching practices in the classroom during oral recitations, and the percentage distribution to show the frequency of occurrences of the students' reasons for code-switching in the classroom.

The purposively chosen participants of the study were the twenty-eight (28) third year students enrolled in the Bachelor in Elementary Education program of San Isidro College, Malaybalay, Bukidnon, Philippines. The instrument used in the study is the researcher's made questionnaire which consisted of four questions as the basis of discussion in the Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Focus Group Discussion (FGD) is a group discussion wherein teachers give an impromptu speaking activity to the students to determine their communicative proficiency in verbal communication. During the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), the students' English-Speaking Proficiency was evaluated through a Rubric of Student Oral language Matrix (SOLOM) for English Speaking Proficiency adapted from the Riverside County Seal of Multiliteracy (2008).

This matrix tests the participants' English-speaking proficiency specifically in the areas of pronunciation, vocabulary, fluency, grammar, and comprehension.

In order to gather data for this study, the researcher obtained permission from the dean of the college of education. After the approval, the following protocols in administering the questionnaire were observed. First, the students were assured that the observation result and the activities would not affect their grades in the subject. They were also reminded of the purpose of the interview, the importance of genuine efforts, and honesty to ensure the validity of the study. To aid in the data collection process, interview questions were presented on a shared screen to assist the interviewee in answering the questions. All interviews were digitally recorded for later transcription and coding.

For documentary analysis and for the purpose of determining the correlative relationship between the participants' extent of code-switching, three (3) English teachers rated the students' English oral proficiency. To detect the respondents' reasons for code-switching, the processes will be done by gathering the essential data through the use of Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The data from the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were gathered, coded, tallied, and statistically treated using the mean, percentage, and frequency of occurrence.

The frequency, mean, standard deviation, and percentage were used to describe the code-switching classification of the students, the reasons for code-switching, and the level of oral English proficiency of the students. T-test will be used to determine the significant relationship between the extent of code switching and the oral English proficiency of the students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher presented information in tables with interpretation and implications. The presentation is organized based on the order of the stated problems in Chapter 1.

1.1. Inter-sentential

Table 1 shows the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' extent of Inter-sentential code-switching. Evidently, with the mean of (M=1.38), the extent of the participants' engagement in inter-sentential code-switching is low. The standard deviation result of 1.66 is not that big which signifies that the inter-sentential code-switching of the students is low extent. The result implies that though the students code-switched during their conversation, their code-switching which involves a clause or sentence boundary is very limited.

The majority or more than half of the participants are code-switching inter-sententially at varying extents having a "low extent" as the highest

Table 1. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Extent of Code-Switching in terms of Inter-sentential Classification.

Range	Description	f	%	Mean	S.D.	Q.I.
7	Very Great Extent	1	3.60	1.38	1.66	Low Extent
5-6	Great Extent	1	3.60			
3-4	Moderate Extent	4	14.30			
1-2	Low Extent	12	42.90			
0	No Code Switching	10	35.60			
Total		28	100			

The scenario below manifests the students' usage of inter-sentential code-switching during the focus group discussion: It also manifests the students' usage of intra-sentential code-switching during the focus group discussion:

- S1:** *Five to ten years from now, I see myself as a professional teacher and I really don't know what future holds us. But feel nko kay musunuray ko sa ila larga ug Thailand (laugh)*
- S3:** *For me ma'am, I will be professional teacher and having a big house (laugh). Mao ra na maam*
- S4:** *I want to be professional teacher and can help my parents. Para malipay pud sila sa akoo.*
- S5:** *The best experience was teaching demo. It somehow gives us an experience to teach. Karon online, pero naghatag gihapon sa ako ug chance nga magtudlo.*
- S9:** *So for me ma'am, may advise for the upcoming college is don't give up for your dreams and put God in the center of your life. Laban lang sa buhay. Mao ra ma'am.*

In these scenarios, code-switching is manifested among the participants of the focus group discussion. English phrases and sentences are mixed with the following vernacular phrases and sentences: *nko kay musunuray ko sa ila larga, Mao ra na maam, Para malipay pud sila sa akoo. pero naghatag gihapon sa ako ug chance nga magtudlo and Laban lang sa buhay. Mao ra ma'am.* In the sample classroom scenario of code-switching, the result of the participants' extent of code-switching inter-sentientally. Was validated.

1.2. Intra-sentential

Table 2 discloses the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' extent of intra-sentential code-switching. Clearly, 13 (46.40%) students out of 28 engaged in intra-sentential code-switching which was described as *low extent*. The data inferred that during the conversation, the participants inserted Visayan and Tagalog into a sentence while speaking the English language. However, the data reveals that the majority of the students code-switched. Only 5 (17.80%) out of 28 students did not code-switched.

Table 2. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Extent of Code-Switching in terms of Intra-sentential Classification

Range	Description	f	%	Mean	S.D.	Q.I.
11-13	Very Great Extent	1	3.60			
8-10	Great Extent	1	3.60			
4-7	Moderate Extent	8	28.60	4.28	3.37	Moderate Extent
1-3	Low Extent	13	46.40			
0	No Code Switching	5	17.80			
Total		28	100			

- S3:** *Ahhmm, for me ma'am kay I think, ahmm, bi, (laugh) Yes, I am prepared, para lang sa ako Ma'am ha, prepared ko katung because San Isidro College kanang molded us to be kanang ready na for the future.*
- S6:** *For me, ma'am, I'm not yet prepared ma'am because when I finished my studies here in San Isidro College, I want to relax sa muna ma'am*
- S8:** *To be honest, for me po, I think I'm not ready because there are still a lot of things na I should learn po, just like sa atung situation karun ahhh, pandemic, dapat ahh, as teachers, we should be prepared for the future. Kulang ta, hands -on jud*

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- S9:** *The significant learning that I have was during the pre-pandemic face-to-face pa when we had our teaching demo, kanang, we really ano ma'am, we really had the best experience on kanang, mura bitaw siyag kanang, very very best because we were able to experience to teach in front of many.*
- S21:** *The significant experience was kay katung kanang teaching demo because kanang kuan bitaw ma'am kanang try unsaun pagteach.*

In the scenarios cited, code-switching was manifested during the focus group discussion. English words are mixed with the following vernacular words: ahh, kay, para lang sa ako, kanang, na, sa muna, po, no, karun ahh, dapat, kulang ta, kuan, bitaw, unsaun, ano, po and jud. The classroom scenario of code-switching also validates the result of the participants' extent of code-switching intra-sententially.

Table 3 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' extent of intra-word code-switching. As revealed in the data, none of the participants code-switched in the morpheme boundaries.

Table 3. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distributions of the Participants' Extent of Code-Switching in terms of Intra-word Classification

Range	Description	f	%	Mean	S.D.	Q.I.
7	Very Great Extent	0	0.0			
5-6	Great Extent	0	0.0			
3-4	Moderate Extent	0	0.0	0	0	No Code Switching
1-2	Low Extent	0	0.0			
0	No Code Switching	28	100			
Total		28	100.0			

Table 4 unveils the overall mean and standard deviation of the five components of English-speaking proficiency. Evidently, the summary table exposes that the majority of the participants rated "good" in all components of the English-speaking proficiency. It could be noticed that the mean of the students' speaking proficiency is *very low*. Data suggest the need for interventions to improve the English-speaking proficiency of the students.

Table 4. Summary Table of the Participants' Oral Proficiency

Oral Proficiency	Mean	Interpretation	S.D.
Comprehension	2.81	Good	0.43
Fluency	2.87	Good	0.40
Vocabulary	2.81	Good	0.39
Pronunciation	2.96	Good	0.41
Grammar	2.69	Good	0.46
Overall	2.83	Good	0.38

Legend: 4.51-5.00 Excellent 2.51-3.50 Good 1.01-1.50 Poor
3.51-4.50 Very Good 1.51-2.50 Fair

Table 5 reveals the test of the relationship between the participants' extent of code-switching and their oral English Proficiency. The data expose that there is a negatively very weak correlation (-0.191) between the participants' inter-sentential code-switching and their comprehension. This implies that there is a very slight increase in comprehension for every decrease of usage in inter-sentential code. Furthermore, there is a negatively very weak correlation (-0.178) between the participants' intra-sentential code-switching and their comprehension. This implies that there is a very slight increase in comprehension for every decrease of usage in intra-sentential code.

Table 5. Result of the Test of Relationship between the Participants' Extent of Code-Switching and their Oral English Proficiency

Oral English Proficiency	Inter-sentential		Intra-sentential	
	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Comprehension	-0.191	0.238	-0.178	0.272
Fluency	-0.200	0.216	-0.141	0.385
Vocabulary	-0.083	0.613	0.035	0.829
Pronunciation	-0.067	0.681	-0.152	0.349
Grammar	0.018	0.910	-0.092	0.572

In the fluency component of the English proficiency, there is a negatively weak correlation (-0.200) between the participants' inter-sentential code-switching and their fluency. This implies that there is a slight increase in fluency for every decrease of usage in inter-sentential code. There is a negatively very weak correlation (-0.141) between the participants' intra-sentential code-switching and their fluency. This implies that there is a very slight increase in fluency for every decrease of usage in intra-sentential code.

For the vocabulary component of the English proficiency, there is a negatively very weak correlation (-0.083) between the participants' inter-sentential code-switching and their vocabulary. This implies that there is a very slight increase in the vocabulary for every decrease of usage in inter-sentential code. Furthermore, there is a positively very weak correlation (0.035) between the participants' intra-sentential code-switching and their vocabulary. This implies that there is a very slight increase in the vocabulary for every increase of usage in intra-sentential code.

As for the pronunciation component of the English-speaking proficiency, there is a negatively very weak correlation (-0.067) between the participants' inter-sentential code-switching and their pronunciation. This implies that there is a slight increase in pronunciation for every decrease of usage in inter-sentential code. There is a negatively very weak correlation (-0.152) between the participants' intra-sentential code-switching and their pronunciation. This implies that there is a slight increase in pronunciation for every decrease of usage in intra-sentential code.

In the grammar component of the English-speaking proficiency, there is a positively very weak correlation (0.018) between the participants' inter-sentential code-switching and their grammar. This implies that there is a slight increase in grammar for every increase of usage in inter-sentential code. There is a negatively very weak correlation (-0.092) between the participants' intra-sentential code-switching and their grammar. This implies that there is a slight increase in grammar for every decrease of usage in inter-sentential code.

Table 6. Participants' Reasons for Code Switching

Theme	<i>f</i>	%
Limited English Language Proficiency	21	75.0
Lacks confidence in expressing	4	14.3
Stressing or emphasizing a point	1	3.6
Deeply rooted in the native language	2	7.1
Total	28	100.0

Limited English Language Proficiency:

S1: For me ah, for my reason because I forgot the word to use while the speaking the sentence.

S4: For me, ahm, same also, (laughing) yes ma'am.

S6: For me, I can't deliver direct English.

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- S8:** *For me, like them because I can't speak straight English well.*
- S11:** *Para sa ako ma'am is, ga-ahm, lack of English japun ma'am, kanang dili namu, dili namu malitok ang English ma'am mau maka bisaya mi.*
- S21:** *Nganung magbisaya because I lack English*
- S23:** *... maglisud ko remember sa word*
- S24:** *para sa ako ahm, naa man gud some words nga dili naku masabtan...*
- S25:** *sa ako mam, ky naandan naman gud natu pgka bisaya.*
- S26:** *ang ako kay dili kaayu kabalua mo English and...*
- S27:** *sa akua mam kky wala ko kabalua ang saktu nga grammar sa englih...*
- S28:** *para sa akua is kung unsa ang naandan ky mau naman gd tong naa satug utok..*
- S29:** *lisud e pronounces....*
- S30:** *... Math English...*
- S31:** *I do code-switching because sometimes kay kuan malimtan nako ang word nga enlisg atung word.*
- S32:** *parehas ra sa iyang ge ingun am nga usahaya dili maka staright enlgish ky mg huanhuna paka sa word..*
- S33:** *... nay mga words nnga malimtan nimu... lisud sya e lituk mam*
- S35:** *maulaw ko nga ma wrong grammar ko.*
- S36:** *para sa akua mam ky naa man gud maayu sa written mam...*
- S37:** *because they want t to expound their ideas.*
- S6:** *for me ang isa ka word ky... mglisud ta og explain sa English*

Lacks Confidence in Expressing:

- S5:** *For me, because I felt nervous and, (laughing...) that's sorry.*
- S7:** *For me, ahm, I'm so nervous and I forget the words that I think to myself.*
- S2:** *For me, so nervous and (laughing), and, and I can't speak English and so it.*
- S1:** *for me mam, I feel nervous and I cannot say the...*

Stressing or Emphasizing a Point:

- S28:** *mas anand man gudta mg bisaya mam... og kuan mam, mg code switching... and mg code switching man gud ta ky madugay ta og hunahuna*

Deeply Rooted in Native Language:

- S3:** *Ahm, for me I cannot, ah, I cannot even talk, ahm, more in foreign language but more in vernacular.*
- S34:** *ako mam ky akong rason ky.. love nako atung sariling wika...*

From the data, the reasons for code-switching given by the students were categorized into four themes namely: limited English Language Proficiency; lacks confidence in expressing; stressing, or emphasizing a point; and deeply rooted in the native language. As shown in Table 6, the higher percentage represents the participants' "Limited English Language Proficiency" (75.0%). The second reason is the participants' *lack of confidence in expressing* in which 4 (14.3%) students out of 28 answered. *Deeply rooted in the native language* is the third reason for the participants' code-switching. Lastly, *stressing or emphasizing a point* is also one of the reasons for code-switching. They said they can deliver the point clearly when they code-switched. This implies that the participants were unsystematic and committed language errors that may lead to misunderstanding of the conversation.

Many online students are afraid of being laughed at, or worst, being mocked when they incorrectly pronounce and use a grammatically erroneous sentence. According to Yan-hua, (2007) students fail to actively participate in the online English discussion because of their English

proficiency problems. Code-mixing takes place when the students have restricted vocabulary. When they speak English, they find themselves in such a position that they do not have an appropriate word to express in that language. Therefore, they use code-mixing because of their restricted English proficiency.

Furthermore, “stressing or emphasizing a point”, is one of the reasons for code-switching among the participants’. There was 1 (3.6%), out of 28 participants who was emphasizing or stressing the particular point in which he was incapable of sufficiently emphasizing the importance of a concept.

The last reason for the students’ code-switching usage is “deeply rooted in native language”. There were 2 (7.1%) out of 28 participants who prefer to use vernacular or their respective dialects because according to them, they felt more comfortable and can easily convey the correct messages when they use their mother tongue.

Generally, the overall reason for the participants to code-switch is inevitably the lack of the target language in which they cannot grasp the target words they want to utter.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the data gathered, the following are the major findings as revealed in this study.

1. The participants showed a low extent of Inter-sentential code-switching with a mean of 1.38 (SD=1.66). The participants’ extent intra-sentential code-switching is at moderate extent with a mean of 4.28 (SD= 3.37). None of the participants had code-switched in the morpheme boundaries, so the participants’ extent of intra-word code-switching is none.
2. The participants showed a good or moderate level of English proficiency in all components, namely: fluency, vocabulary, comprehension, grammar, and pronunciation.
3. There is no significant association between the participants’ extent of code-switching and their Oral English Proficiency.
4. Factors like lack of confidence, limited English Language Proficiency, stressing or emphasizing a point, and being deeply rooted in the native language are identified why online students code-switch.

Based on the findings, the study revealed that code-switching influences interlocutors’ English Speaking Proficiency, though there is a weak correlation between the extents of code-switching and the student's English proficiency level. This indicates that students often code-switched in both inter-sentential and intra-sentential. The result showed that the comprehension, fluency, pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary component of the participants is good.

In general, code-switching effects in this study are widely perceived as negative. There is a possibility to view code-switching as a barrier to learning and as being disruptive to the English language learning environment. Others have a different view, however, in particular, that code-switching may be perceived as ‘linguistic resourcefulness’ by overcoming the lack of a suitable word in the second language.

Yet, the English-speaking proficiency level of the students revealed a need to help the students improve their linguistic skills. The findings point to the need for the school to initiate short-term program or interventions and encourage teachers to establish speaking activities for successful learning and mastery of the English language as well as to improve language competence and vocabulary.

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